

USE OF ELEMENTS AND ECOLOGICAL FORMATION

Ashurova Oygul Anvarjonovna

Teacher of Fergana State University

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7883444>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 22th April 2023

Accepted: 29th April 2023

Online: 30th April 2023

KEY WORDS

Humanitarian - ecological discourse, ecological aesthetics, esthetics, aesthetics of nature.

ABSTRACT

The possibility of applying the concept "transformed form" within the framework of the aesthetics of nature and environmental aesthetics is substantiated; justified interpretation of environmental aesthetics as a kind of transformed form of aesthetics of nature.

INTRODUCTION.

In modern science, the term "ecology" is not limited to the biological meaning, because it cannot be excluded from its application to man and society. Applied to society, the biological side of this concept appears in unity with social, ecological, and technical factors of people's lives.

A lot has been done to improve the system of scientific knowledge about nature, reflected in educational programs and textbooks. The process of studying nature and communication of students with it is given an active character, since the formation of relationships with reality, including the natural environment.

THE MAIN PART.

Through the analysis of the existing pedagogical experience, it is possible to highlight pedagogical tools aimed at the formation of ecological and aesthetic education in primary school.

Pedagogical experience means such pedagogical practice that creatively uses the best theory, brings innovation and paves the way to the unknown, which allows to improve the quality and results of educational activities.

During the analysis of the pedagogical experience, the basic principles of natural history and science in primary school, which must be taken into account when developing a methodical product, are highlighted.

K.P. Yagodovsky (1877-1943) - the author of a large number of works on the method of teaching science in primary school: "Lessons in science in primary school", "Practical lessons in science in primary school", "How to teach science in primary school", "Living corner" in the school and at home", "Ugolki nature in the elementary school", "Practice teaching natural science" and others.

In works K.P. For the first time, Yagodovsky clearly and convincingly revealed the psychological need of children of primary school age to study nature. He believed that the

decisive factor in building a system of acquiring knowledge about nature in elementary school should be the methodologically appropriate selection of material for study, as well as the education of students' skills in dealing with concrete facts.

The book "Questions of general methodical science" is the result of all his scientific activities. Considering the issue of the formation of concepts, the author pays special attention to the guidance of the cognitive process of the teacher in educational work, he believes that "the methodology begins from the moment when the teacher becomes the leader of the cognitive process occurring in the mind of the student".

P.A. Zavitaev (1890-1970) made a significant contribution to the method of teaching natural science in primary classes. In his works, he strove to show how to form natural science ideas and concepts using methods that are characteristic of natural sciences. The developed method of conducting observations, experiments and excursions helps to create a concrete - emotional basis for the formation of natural science concepts. P.A. Zavitaev defined a system of subject lessons, defined their content and methodology ("Excursions and subject lessons in I-IV classes"). Much attention is paid to ten special classes at the school site ("Educational-experimental site of I-IV classes", "Work of students of I-IV classes at the educational-experimental site"), where students acquire skills and abilities to grow plants. Ten considered that natural science constitutes the initial stage of polytechnic education of students.

M.N. Skatkin (1900-1991) - methodologist for teaching science in primary classes and polytechnic education of schoolchildren; the author of the elementary school science program; the author of natural science textbooks for classes III and IV. I created a series of visual aids, tables, pictures, collections, movies, as well as methodical instructions for their application in lessons.

Irina Trofimovna Vepreva - doctor of philological sciences, professor. Emphasizes the importance of the formation of ecological and aesthetic culture. "The common task of all educational areas, each academic discipline is the task of developing independence and creativity of thinking, developing the ability to work in a group, perception of external criticism, free expression of judgments and argumentation of one's point of view. The inclusion of everyone in real environmental activities, as a combination of environmental protection, adaptive and self-management (decision-making in environmental situations), will allow to educate not only intelligence and emotions, but also the will, to develop practical skills of an ecological nature.

Irina Trofimovna emphasizes in her books: "...one cannot limit himself to the theory of step-by-step formation of mental activity: for solving environmental problems, the main task is the formation of concepts and the implementation of this activity, both in the educational situation and in real life." He draws attention to the fact that the formation of environmental literacy must take place in practice in reality. In his practice, he applied such a form of organization, which should be supplemented with a situational approach; which ensures decision-making in a concrete, real, unresolved, or model (as in problem-based learning) situation and should include the following stages:

- 1) analysis situation;
- 2) detection problem;

- 3) alternative development;
- 4) definition of selection criteria;
- 5) choice (prinyati reshni);
- 6) practical implementation solutions;
- 7) evaluation efficiency solution.

On the basis of the analysis of pedagogical experience, the following methods and techniques were selected, which are reflected in the collection of lesson designs aimed at the formation of ecological and aesthetic culture of junior schoolchildren. Namely such as:

- organization of observations in nature;
- organization of didactic games for lessons;
- organization of reading ecological tales.

Based on all of the above, it can be concluded that many works of modern researchers consider the environment as the main pedagogical tool for the formation of ecological and aesthetic culture of younger schoolchildren in the lessons of the environment, and emphasize the importance of using active methods. For the formation of accurate representations of children about natural phenomena, it is necessary to use visual methods: these are tables, pictures, video films, collections. However, it should be noted that for the formation of the educational component of ecological and aesthetic culture, it is necessary to involve children in active activities.

CONCLUSION.

Thus, based on the analysis of pedagogical experience, it is possible to conclude that environmental problems can and should be solved through interaction with the environment and study of environmental issues in the lessons of the environment. This educational and methodological support guarantees the achievement of the highest results, as well as the development of cognitive learning activities during the lessons.

References:

1. Akhmadjonova, O. A. (2021). Symbolic And Figurative Images Used In The Novel "Chinar". *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(03), 389-392.
2. Oripova, G. M., Akhmadjonova, O. A., Kholmatov, O. U. U., & Muminova, T. S. (2022). INTERPRETATION OF MOTHER IMAGE IN LITERATURE. *International scientific journal of Biruni*, 1(2), 304-309.
3. Akhmadjonova, O. A., & Shavkatovna, D. M. Sabirdinov Akbar G'afurovich, SA Xo'jaev, & H. Jo'raev.(2022, May 1). CREATIVE WORLD.
4. Xo'jaev, S. A., Akhmadjonova, O. A., Shavkatovna, D. M., G'afurovich, S. A., & Jo'raev, H. (2022). ULUGBEK HAMDAM'S UNUSUAL LOVE THREE IN" MUVOZANAT" NOVEL.
5. Akhmadjonova Okilakhon Abdumalikovna. (2023). PORTRAIT OF THE WOMAN'S SPIRIT IN THE ARTWORK. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 4(1), 508-514.
6. Tursunova, D. (2022). FACTORS INFLUENCING THE FORMATION OF SOCIAL ACTIVITY. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(12), 285-289.

7. Tursunova, D. (2022). PRIORITY PRINCIPLES AND PJTIMO-PEDAGOGICAL FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL ACTIVITY IN FEMALE STUDENTS. *Science and Innovation*, 1(3), 523-529.
8. qizi Tursunova, D. T. (2021). Principal And Important Factors In The Formation Of Social Activity Student Women. *Current Research Journal Of Pedagogics*, 2(05), 53-62.
9. Maxamadaliyevna, Y. D. O „ljayevna, ORF (2020). Tursunova Dilnavoz To „lqin qizi, Sharofutdinova Ra" noxon Shavkatovna, Ashurova Oygul Anvarovna. Pedagogical features of mental development of preschool children. *Solid State Technology*, 63(6).
10. Tursunova, D. (2022). PUBLIC ACTIVITIES AND ITS PERSONS. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMYIY JURNALI*, 127-130.
11. Ashurova, O. A. (2021). AESTHETIC EDUCATION AS A FACTOR OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF PRESCHOOL TEACHERS IN A PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITY. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 425-427.
12. Ashurova, O. (2021). Analysis of foreign experience on the development of eco-aesthetic culture of future preschool education specialists. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*, 10(10), 1478-1484.
13. Ashurova, O. A. (2021). SOCIO-HISTORICAL TRADITIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF ECOESTHETIC CULTURE OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL PROFESSIONALS. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 2(05), 46-52.
14. Ashurova, O. (2021, December). THE IMPORTANCE OF AESTHETICITY OF ECOLOGICAL CONSCIOUSNESS AND CULTURE IN THE ACTIVITIES OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL PROFESSIONALS. In *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences* (pp. 88-90).
15. Anvarjonovna, A. O. (2021). Factors for the Development of Ecoesthetic Culture of Future Preschool Educational Professionals. *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements*, 2(5), 162-164.
16. Khallokovna, M. E. (2022). Theoretical And Methodological Fundamentals of Improving the Quality of Education in Non-State Educational Institutions. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 11638-11646.
17. Ergashevna, X. M., & Yuldashevna, S. G. (2022). NODAVLAT MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMYIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 19-24.
18. Ergashevna, X. M., & Rasuljonovna, X. R. (2022). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMDA PEDAGOG VA MUTAXASSISLARINING KASBIY KOMPETENTLIGINI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY VA AMALIY JIHATLARI. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMYIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 31-36.
19. Ergashevna, X. M., & Yuldashevna, S. G. (2022). NODAVLAT MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMYIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 19-24.
20. Ergashevna, X. M., & Rasuljonovna, X. R. (2022). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMDA PEDAGOG VA MUTAXASSISLARINING KASBIY KOMPETENTLIGINI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY VA AMALIY JIHATLARI. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMYIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 31-36.
21. Mukhtoraliyevna, Z. S. (2022). INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMYIY JURNALI*, 162-165.

22. Mukhtoraliyevna, Z. S., & Saminjanovna, M. S. (2022). Formation of Future Primary School Teachers Skills to Use Project Activities. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 6, 346-353.
23. Zokirova, S. M. (2016). About the congruent phenomenon in the contrastive linguistics. *Sciences of Europe*, (8-2 (8)), 45-46.
24. Muxtoraliyevna, Z. S. (2023). BOSHLANG 'ICH SINF O 'QUVCHILARINING IMLOSI USTIDA ISHLASHDA DIDAKTIK O 'YINLARDAN FOYDALANISH. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(2), 473-478.
25. Zokirova, S. M. (2020). Ta'limda axborot texnologiyalarining vujudga kelish tarixi. *Молодой ученый*, (18), 586-587.
26. Уринова, Ф. У. (2022). ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ПСИХОЛОГИИ РЕБЁНКА ДОШКОЛЬНОГО И МЛАДШЕГО ШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА. *Science and innovation*, 1(B2), 68-71.
27. Uljayevna, U. F. (2022). THE ACTIVITY OF DEVELOPMENTAL CENTERS IN THE FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S ABILITIES. *Science and innovation*, 1(B2), 107-110.
28. Uljaevna, U. F. (2022). Development of creative activity of preschool children in art game as a psychological and pedagogical problem. *barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 47-51.
29. Tojimamatovich, J. V. . (2023). Digital Transformation of Educational Management System. *Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education*, 2(4), 202-206.
30. Tojimamatovich, J. V. . (2023). [CONCEPT AND ESSENCE OF INFORMATION SECURITY](#). *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 2 (4), 643-647